

Speculation on Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution From a Microcanonical Power Law Part III

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 5, 2023

In (1), a probability distribution is obtained for a two-dimensional vector. This distribution is based on a constant probability for the angle θ i.e. $P(\theta) d\theta = C d\theta$. In other words, a vector is associated with a physical rotation as seen by a physical co-ordinate system, we argue. We further argue that there is a physical constraint for the vector to move from θ_1 to θ_2 through the θ values in between. It cannot jump from one to the other, rather it rotates. It is this rotation, as opposed to jumping motion which characterizes the probability distribution based on $d\theta$.

We consider the situation of two numbers, e_1, e_2 constrained by $e_1 + e_2 = E$ ((1)), with $e_1 > 0$ and $e_2 > 0$. One may write $e_1 = p_1 p_1$ and $e_2 = p_2 p_2$, where p_1 and p_2 may be positive or negative. Then ((1)) becomes $p_1 p_1 + p_2 p_2 = RR$ where $E = RR$. This has the form of $x^2 + y^2 = r^2$. (x, y) , however, is a vector because there exists a physical co-ordinate system and the change in x, y must move from one θ_1 to another θ_2 by passing through the θ values in between. This constrains the changes in x and y . e_1 and e_2 , however, have no such physical constraint. As a result, in Part II we suggested a probability distribution for $e_1 + e_2 = E$ in the following manner. For a given e_1 , $e_2 = E - e_1$. Thus each e_1 is matched with only one energy state and so has the same probability, i.e. $P(e) de = C de$.

In (2), $e_1 + e_2 = E$ is represented by $p_1 p_1 + p_2 p_2 = RR$ for two one-dimensionally moving particles. p_1 and p_2 are then the momenta of the particles and are taken seriously as being part of a vector. This approach is then generalized to n particles, i.e. an n -dimensional sphere. We argue that there is no physical reason to introduce a vector in this situation as there is no physical rotation and hence no reason to have constrained motion through a series of θ values.

Two Vector Probability

(1) deals with the calculation of two-vector probability. We define a vector as not only a set of two numbers (a, b) constrained by $a^2 + b^2 = r^2$, but by the existence of a physical co-ordinate system and a physical rotation which constrains motion through θ , an angle. In other words, the vector is physically forced to move from θ_1 to $\theta_1 + d\theta$ etc. It cannot suddenly jump from θ_1 to a completely different θ_2 . This is constrained motion and affects the probability distribution, we argue.

Following (1) one has:

$$P(\theta) d\theta = C d\theta \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{For a vector } (B_x, B_y) \text{ with magnitude } B: \quad B_x = B \cos(\theta) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Then: } dB_x = B |\sin(\theta)| d\theta \quad ((3))$$

((3)) shows that dBx is constrained by physical rotational motion which forces one to move from one θ to $\theta + d\theta$ etc. ((3)) describes the constraint of physical rotation.

$$P(\theta) d\theta = C dBx / (B|\sin(\theta)|) \quad ((4))$$

The Case of $e_1+e_2=E$ with $e_1>0, e_2>0$

Consider the problem of $e_1+e_2=E$ with $e_1>0, e_2>0$. One may write $e_1=p_1^2/2m$ and $e_2=p_2^2/2m$ to show that e_1 and e_2 are constrained to be positive. Then:

$$p_1^2 + p_2^2 = R^2 \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is of the same form as a vector magnitude squared equation: $x^2+y^2=r^2$, but there is no physical rotation associated. In other words, one is not constrained to move from θ_1 to $\theta_1+d\theta$ etc. One may jump from one p_1, p_2 set to another, as long as ((5)) is satisfied. Thus the approach of two-vector, described in the above section, does not apply, we argue.

Instead, we use the following approach. Given a value for e_1 for particle 1, the value of energy for e_2 is automatically $E-e_1$. In other words, each e_1 value only has one corresponding state for e_2 . Thus, we argue that $P(e)de = Cde$. The probability is constant and not given by the vector result, as there is no constrained motion.

N Particles and N-Sphere Probability

In (2), a system of n one-dimensional particles is constrained by:

$$\sum_i e_i = E \quad \text{with } e_i = p(i)^2/2m \quad ((6)) \quad \text{Then:}$$

$\sum_i p(i)^2 = R^2$ where $E=R^2/2m$ and $p(i)$ is the one-dimensional momentum of particle i .

2Treats ((6)) as an n -sphere, i.e. introduces the notion of a physical vector, but we argue that there is no physical vector and no constrained motion in a circle. In particular, in (2) the n th particle is assigned a particular value $p(n)$ and:

$$R\sin(\theta) = p(n)/R \quad ((7)) \quad \text{and } R\cos(\theta)R\cos(\theta) = R^2 - p(n)^2 \quad ((7))$$

A constrained circular motion based on θ is introduced, which we object to.

A given $p(n)$ value then corresponds to $R^2 - p(n)^2$ energy for the $n-1$ remaining particles, which are said to define an $n-1$ sphere. The area of this sphere then represents the corresponding probability. This approach leads to:

$$P(p) dp = dp C \sqrt{1 - p^2/R^2} \text{ power}(n-3) \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{For } n=2, \text{ one has: } P(p) dp = dp C \sqrt{1 - p^2/R^2} \text{ power}(-1) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is the vector probability for a 2-vector given in the first section. This, however, is based on motion constrained to a circle, i.e. motion from θ_1 to $\theta_1 + d\theta$ etc. We argue that such a constraint does not exist, and so one should not use the probability for a 2-vector, but rather the value from section (2). For $n > 2$, we have shown in Part II that one obtains:

$$P(e)de = C (E-e)^{n-2} \quad ((10))$$

((10)) leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann form $\exp(-e/E)$ in the high n limit. If one sets the E limit to $E \rightarrow \infty$, then one may argue for replacing E with a parameter T in $\exp(-e/E)$ such that:

$$C \int dp \exp(-e/T) = 1 \text{ and } C \int dp e \exp(-e/T) = Eave = E/n \quad ((11)) \text{ Here } e = pp/2m \text{ in one-dimension.}$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a physical vector must be linked with a physical rotation associated with physical co-ordinates. It represents a constrained motion (i.e. rotation). In particular, one may not jump from one point on a circle to a completely different one. One must rather rotate. This accounts for the constrained motion of B_x in (B_x, B_y) a 2-vector as shown in section 1.

If one has two positive numbers $e_1 + e_2 = E$, one may write $p_1^2 + p_2^2 = RR$. This has the same form as a vector magnitude squared, but one does not have a vector because there is no physical constrained rotational motion. One may jump from any (p_1, p_2) value to another, provided $p_1^2 + p_2^2 = RR$, without moving through the corresponding θ values. Thus, we argue that the vector probability given in section 1 does not apply and one should use the approach of section 2.

References

1. F.Reif Fundamentals of Statistical and Thermal Physics McGraw-Hill (1965)
2. Lopez-Ruiz, R. and Calbet, Z. Why the Maxwell Distribution is the Attractive Fixed Point of the Boltzmann Equation 2006 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/nlin/0611044.pdf>